

CEPHIA

*Consortium for the Evaluation and
Performance of HIV Incidence Assays*

SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence ELA

Evaluation Report

**Blood Systems
Research Institute**

**Public Health
England**

**BILL & MELINDA
GATES foundation**

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DST/NRF Centre of Excellence in Epidemiological Modelling and Analysis

Evaluation of Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA

Enzyme Immunoassay for Population
Estimates of HIV-1 Incidence
Cat. No. 1000

CEPHIA PROJECT TEAM

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Table of Contents

Summary	4
Background	5
CEPHIA	5
Introduction	6
Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA	7
Description of Assay	7
Summary and explanation of test	7
Principles of the procedure	7
Table 1 Assay information Summary	9
Evaluation panel and method	12
Analysis of Assay Characteristics	19
Definition of assay characteristics	19
Data analysis methods	20
Results	23
Conclusions and Recommendations	33
Technical Appraisal	34
Assay kits and reagents	34
Equipment	34
Associated documents	35
Technical conclusions	37
Target Product Profile performance	38
Acknowledgements	40
References	41
Appendix - Evaluation Protocol	42
CEPHIA project management contact details	44
Manufacturer's comments	46
Enquires	53

Summary - SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA

Background

Monitoring the prevalence of HIV provides a blunt tool for understanding both recent transmission rates and the impact of behavioural changes or public health interventions on these rates. Consequently, there has been increasing application of assays, which are able to distinguish between ‘recently’ acquired HIV-1 infections and ‘long-standing’ infections, in cross-sectional surveys, to estimate HIV incidence. A comparative analysis of these existing incidence assays is a logical and necessary next step to facilitate the introduction of HIV incidence assays into wide use.

Evaluation Panel

The ‘evaluation panel’ consists of 2 500 uniquely-labelled HIV+ plasma specimens obtained from 928 distinct subjects, and was provided in 5 sets of 500 specimens each. 75 of these specimens represent 25 aliquots of each of 3 underlying specimens, and acted as (unmarked) controls. Laboratories were blinded to the specimen background information.

Data Analysis

The assay characteristics, namely the mean duration of recent infection (MDRI – average time ‘recent’ while infected for less than some time T) and false-recent rate (FRR – probability of a ‘recent’ result for an individual infected for longer than T), were estimated in a number of specimen sets. The MDRI (excluding treated subjects and identified elite controllers) is 302 days (95% CI: 274-331), for $T=2$ years and a Western blot HIV diagnostic test. The FRR in this specimen set is 7% (95% CI: 4-11%). High FRRs occur amongst treated subjects (>60%), elite controllers (>15%) and virally suppressed subjects (>50%).

Technical Appraisal

This assay is a commercially available assay developed specifically for the purpose of differentiating recent from long standing infections for use in studying cross-sectional studies. It is a manual EIA and requires apparatus available to most laboratories. There are two reagent packs one of which requires storage at -25°C to -10°C and the other at 2 to 8°C. An EQA scheme and training in performance of the assay is available from CDC, Atlanta. Data management software for interpretation of the assay is available from the manufacturer. The assay is simple to perform following training.

Conclusions

This does not reach the current Target Product Profile (TPP) for use in cross sectional incidence assays and we do not recommend its use.

Background

In recent years it has become recognized that monitoring of the current burden, or prevalence, of HIV infection in populations is a blunt tool for understanding both recent transmission trends and the impact of behavioural change and public health interventions on those trends. Tests able to distinguish recently-acquired HIV-1 infections from long-standing ones by testing a single serum specimen from an infected individual, and by applying them to cross-sectional serosurveys to estimate population incidence rates, are being increasingly used. The term RITA (Recent Infection Test Algorithm) has been coined to describe assays and combinations of assays and other (clinical) criteria that are able to identify recent HIV infection. While any of several assays may be used within a RITA, each of them is dependent first and foremost on employing highly sensitive methods to detect and confirm the presence of anti- HIV-1 antibodies in the specimen. A method is then employed whose signal takes considerably longer to exceed a threshold above which the specimen is considered to be from a long-standing infection. The methods rely on the generalisation that the signal measured increases gradually, and at a similar rate, in each infected individual, over a period of several months following primary HIV infection and seroconversion

It has been recognized at various meetings of the WHO Technical Working Group on Incidence Assays that a statistically sound comparative analysis of existing incidence assays is a logical and necessary next step to facilitate the introduction of HIV incidence assays into wide use. In 2011, The Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded a project '*Development of specimen repository and evaluation of assays for identification of recent HIV infection and estimation of HIV incidence*' to help facilitate this aim.

CEPHIA

The **Consortium for the Evaluation and Performance of HIV Incidence Assays** (CEPHIA) brings together world leaders in the development, performance and application of RITA assays that are able to identify recent HIV infection. CEPHIA's purpose is to successfully deliver the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded project and to advance the understanding of currently available assays that can identify recent HIV infection; to better describe the duration of the infection state in which they identify recent infection; and to determine the rate at which they misclassify specimens as from recent infections.

Specific project objectives are to evaluate and compare currently available assays for use in the measurement of recent HIV infection using a common set of specimens collected for this purpose and to assess the ability of the assays, alone or in combination, to accurately estimate HIV incidence in populations.

An overview of CEPHIA, related documentation and updates is available at <http://www.incidence-estimation.org/page/cephia-overview>

Appendix 2 details CEPHIA Group members

Introduction

As part of the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded project, 'Development of specimen repository and evaluation of assays for identification of recent HIV infection and estimation of HIV incidence', the CEPHIA group undertook evaluations of a number of available assays. This report details the results of the evaluation of the **Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA**.

Initial evaluation of this assay used a 'CEPHIA Qualification Panel' of specimens to determine the potential the assay had in determining HIV recency before a full evaluation was undertaken. CDC were responsible for providing the kits and test method used for the evaluation. Testing was performed by four CEPHIA approved testing sites which all completed a CDC hosted training session in the use of the assay prior to undertaking the evaluation.

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2. BSRI - Blood Systems Research Institute, San Francisco, California, USA
3. CDC - Centers for Disease Control, Atlanta, Georgia, USA
4. JHU – John Hopkins University, Baltimore, USA

Full evaluation of the **Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA** was considered justified following review of the qualification panel data by the CEPHIA management team and due to its previous widespread use in a number of studies. Evaluation Panel testing was performed at Public Health England, London.

The 2,425 HIV+ plasma specimens used for the evaluation were sourced by the CEPHIA team at UCSF – University of California and comprised a wide range of suitable and challenging specimen types. Tables 3 - 5 summarises the specimen types used in the evaluation.

All evaluation data was analysed by the CEPHIA team at SACEMA - South African Centre for Epidemiological Modelling and Analysis, Stellenbosch, South Africa

SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA Information

The evaluation was performed during 2013. Performance and interpretation of the assay was undertaken using the Kit inserts applicable to each batch of tests used. In preparation of the this report we have used kit insert version LN 6011.04 as this was the latest kit insert available when analysis of the results was undertaken. Sedia have informed us that further updated versions of the kit insert are available. We are grateful to Sedia for permission to reproduce excerpts of their kit insert.

Description of Assay

The Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA is an *in vitro* quantitative enzyme immunoassay for distinguishing recent HIV-1 infections from those which are long-term. The test measures the proportion of HIV-1 specific IgG to total IgG in blood samples including plasma, serum, and dried blood, plasma, and serum spots. The Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA is solely intended for research use only such as estimating HIV-1 incidence in a population, monitoring and evaluating intervention programs, and recognizing those high-incidence populations so that prevention research, vaccine trials, and resources are most appropriately utilized. This product is not intended for use in diagnostic procedures or for determining clinical outcome or treatment. (Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA Kit insert LN6011.04)

Summary and explanation of the test

The Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA measures the ratio of HIV-1 specific immunoglobulin G (IgG) to total IgG in a serum or plasma specimen and determines the recent/long term HIV-1 status by referencing the EIA numerical result against that of an internal calibrator specimen. The principle of the test is based on the observation that the ratio of HIV-specific IgG to total IgG is lower in early HIV-1 seroconverters than those with a longer term infection. In fact, studies have suggested that HIV-specific IgG increases for more than two years after seroconversion when tested by the BED EIA. (Taken from kit insert LN6011.04)

Principles of the procedure

1. The Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA is an IgG-capture enzyme immunoassay (C-EIA). During a sample incubation of 60 min. at 37°C, human IgG (including HIV-specific IgG) is captured by goat anti-human IgG coated to the wells of a microplate.
2. Biotinylated HIV-1 BED peptide is incubated for 60 min at 37°C. The peptide is captured only by anti-HIV IgG.
3. Streptavidin-labelled HRP is incubated for 90 min at 37°C and binds to the biotin.

4. TMB substrate is incubated at 25°C and colour is generated with intensity proportional to the amount of HRP.
5. The optical density of each well is measured. The OD value, consistent with the proportion of HIV-specific IgG to total IgG, is divided by the OD value of an internal kit calibrator to generate the normalized OD or “ODn”. The value of the ODn dictates whether a result needs to be confirmed and/or if the HIV infection is recent or long term. (Taken from kit insert LN6011.04)

General Kit Information

The Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA is comprised of two components of matching lot numbers that have separate temperature requirements (frozen and refrigerated). The kit contains two 96-well plates with twelve (12) 1 x 8 removable strips and all necessary reagents to run the assay. Each 1 x 8 strip may be further broken down into individual wells which may be inserted back into the plate frame so that only the exact number of wells required need be used. It is recommended that empty spaces in the plate frame be filled with used wells or strips if using dispensing and/or washing equipment that cannot be programmed on an individual well basis.

A summary of the characteristics of the SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA assay is given in Table 1. The table includes details relating to the kit such as product number, volumes required, completion times, antigens/antibodies used, and the controls/calibrators used. Table 2 quotes claims stated by the manufacturer in the provided kit insert regarding the performance of the assay and its limitations.

SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA Kit Images

Table 1: Assay Information Summary – This version of the assay was used for the evaluation but a version with updated labelling and kit insert is now available.

General	
Assay Name	SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA
Manufacturer	SEDIA Biosciences Corporation
Catalogue Number	1000
Number of Specimens can test/Kit – Screen mode	170 (Screen Mode), 56 (Confirmatory Mode)
Test Volume – Screen mode	5µl (Screen Mode), 5µl x 3 (Confirmatory Mode)
Presentation	
Assay type	In vitro quantitative enzyme immunoassay
Antibodies	Specimen IgG antibody (including HIV-specific)
Reading wavelength	450nm with reference wavelength 620-650nm
Refrigeration pack	2 to 8°C – see below
Antigens (coated microwell plates)	Goat Anti-Human Immunoglobulin (IgG)
Substrate	Contains 3,3',5,5' tetramethyl-benzidine (TMB) in acidic buffer

10X Wash buffer	Phosphate buffered Saline, detergent and a preservative
Stop Solution	Contains dilute acid solution
Freezer Pack	-25°C to -10°C – see below
Conjugate	Streptavidin-HRP conjugate (SA-HRP)
HIV-1 BED Peptide	Biotinylated synthetic peptide that includes divergent gp41 sequences from all HIV-1 subtypes
Calibrator (CAL) (Stored at -25°C to -10°C)	Inactivated human serum reactive to HIV-1 antigens. Non-reactive for HBsAg and antibodies to HCV. Contains preservative.
Low Positive control (LPC) (Stored at -25°C to -10°C)	Inactivated human serum reactive to HIV-1 antigens. Non-reactive for HBsAg and antibodies to HCV. Contains preservative.
High Positive control (HPC) (Stored at -25°C to -10°C)	Inactivated human serum reactive to HIV-1 antigens. Non-reactive for HBsAg and antibodies to HCV. Contains preservative.
Negative control (NC) (Stored at -25°C to -10°C)	Inactivated human serum non-reactive for HBsAg and antibodies to HCV and HIV. Contains preservative.

Stages	
Reagent Preparation time	60 minutes to reach room temp
Specimen Pre-dilution set-up time	30 minutes
Sample/BED peptide/Conjugate/Substrate incubations	60mins/60mins/90mins/15mins
Total time to completion	5.25 hours

Additional Equipment Required	
Serological pipettes and tips	single (2-20ul, 10-100ul), multichannel (200ul)
Positive displacement pipette or microliter syringe capable of delivering 5-20µl	Required to measure out conjugate concentrate
Polypropylene tubes	1.2ml 'titertubes' 12-15ml with cap
Graduated cylinders	100ml, 1000ml
Reagent reservoirs	
Incubators	37°C (±2°C) and 25°C (±2°C)
Vortex Mixer	
Microwell Plate Washer	Either 96-well or strip
Spectrophotometer	450nm with reference filter 620-650nm
Household bleach and Biohazardous waste container	
Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)	Latex gloves, protective safety glasses, lab coat

Table 2: Manufacturer Claims for the assay and its limitations

Claims for the assay (Taken from kit insert LN6011.04)

More comprehensive evaluations with several cohorts from 10 countries with diverse HIV subtypes suggest that the threshold value of $ODn = 0.8$ corresponds to a mean recency period of 197 days with variations among subtype ranging from 127 to 236 days. The same study determined the mean recency period for subtype B as 162 days. The CDC recommends the use of this value for studies where subtype B is prevalent, including the United States. Mean BED recency period (ω) observed for various subtypes on the listed cohort size is shown in the table below:

Subtype (region)	Number of subjects	ω (95% CL)
B (U.S.)	273	162 (146, 179)
C (Africa)	196	203 (162, 243)
AE (Thai)	154	127 (113, 141)
B (Thai)	36	177 (151, 203)
A/D/AG (Africa)	95	236 (199, 273)
Overall	756	197 (173, 220)

Although the BED EIA is designed to reduce differences in mean recency periods between different subtypes, the differences still observed may limit utility of this assay in populations with divergent subtypes. Such populations may require use of subtype-specific recency periods for the accurate estimation of incidence.

The predictive value of any assay depends on the prevalence of that condition in a population. Therefore, the predictive value of detecting recently infected individuals in low incidence populations would be lower than in higher incidence populations. Test attributes, including reproducibility, inter-run and intra-run coefficient of variation (CV), and inter-operator variability has been well studied by CDC scientists prior to commercialization of the assay. These studies suggest that the assay has a very high reproducibility with $R2 > 0.9$.

Limitations of the assay

Classification of individuals by the Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA as recent seroconverters or long-term infections is based on average development of HIV-antibodies calculated from data using a large number of people. However, there are differences among the individuals and the rates at which antibodies are made. Although this assay is useful at the population level, its predictive value for the individual may be low (especially when ODn levels are close to the cut-off). Therefore, the assay should not be used for individual assessment of recency of infection. Some people with long-term HIV infections, including AIDS, may be misclassified as recently infected. Such “False Recency Rates” (FRR) have been reported ranging from 0.8 to 16.1%. Persons with diagnosis of AIDS or low $CD4^+$ T cell counts (below 200 cells per μ l), recipients of antiretroviral therapy and known “elite controllers” (HIV-infected individuals with known low or undetectable viral loads) should be excluded from the study populations to increase the predictive value of the assay.

Evaluation Panel and Method

The ‘evaluation panel’ consists of 2,500 uniquely-labelled HIV+ve plasma specimens obtained from 928 distinct subjects, and was provided to laboratories in 5 sets of 500 specimens each. 75 of these specimens represent 25 aliquots of each of 3 underlying specimens, and acted as (unmarked) controls. Laboratory technicians were blinded to the specimen background information.

Evaluation panel testing is intended to provide the relevant data to estimate assay characteristics, assess and compare assay performance, and optimize the algorithms of assays and biomarkers used in RITAs, for purposes of estimating HIV incidence.

Tables 2 to 6, and Figure 1, describe the sources and characteristics of specimens included in the evaluation panel.

The CEPHIA ‘evaluation panel’ was tested using the SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA following the procedure and validations detailed in the kit insert supplied with the Assay kits. The current kit insert is available from <http://www.sediabio.com/products/bed-eia>

Prior to beginning the evaluation the evaluator(s) attended a training workshop provided by the assay developer – U.S. Centres for Disease Control (CDC) to ensure evaluators were properly trained in the use of the kit and equipment.

The evaluation was conducted under the strict quality requirements as laid out in the CEPHIA Quality Management Strategy (Document 002). Refer to Appendix 1 – Evaluation Protocol for further details.

Assay Kits were stored as requested; the Refrigerator pack was stored at 2-8°C and the Freezer Pack was stored at or below -20°C. This was the case until the manufacturers advised a change in storage conditions for the freezer pack from $\leq -20^{\circ}\text{C}$, to -25°C to -10°C on 27th February 2013 (please note that this is after the testing of the Evaluation Panel was complete). The change in storage temperature was advised because “storage of temperatures below -25°C may result in freezing of the conjugate and repeated freeze/thawing of the Conjugate may result in reduced performance of the assay”. All reagents (except conjugate concentrate) were allowed to reach room temperature before the test was run. The TMB was stored in a 25°C incubator until use.

Two Kit Lots of SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA were used during the evaluation:

KIT LOT: DA1201 supplied with kit insert LN 6011.02
 DH2401 supplied with kit insert LN 6011.03

All equipment (plate washers, pipettes, readers and incubators) had undergone proper installation, operation and performance/monitoring qualification prior to testing to minimise assay variability.

The standard operating procedures for Evaluation Panel testing are available on the project website (<http://www.incidence-estimation.com/page/cephia>)[1].

Table 2: Source of Specimens used in the Evaluation Set

Type of partner site	Site Name	Location of specimen draws
Seroconverter Cohorts		
<i>US and Brazil cohorts enrol subjects diagnosed with acute HIV seroconversion.</i>	UCSF Options Project UCSD Acute HIV Study AMPLIAR	San Francisco San Diego Brazil
<i>IAVI Protocol C enrolls subjects who seroconvert during participation in an HIV incidence cohort study.</i>	IAVI Protocol C	Kenya Rwanda Uganda
<i>All cohorts follow subjects both prior to and after antiretroviral therapy.</i>		South Africa Zambia
HIV+ cohorts		
<i>SCOPE enrolls HIV positive men and women both on and off ARV treatment, actively recruits elite controllers, and follows these subjects over time.</i>	SCOPE San Francisco Men’s Health Study (SFMHS)	San Francisco
<i>SFMHS enrolled both HIV negative and HIV positive men from a population-based sample in SF and followed these subjects forward over time.</i>		
Blood Banks		
<i>Blood banks identify repeat blood donors with a negative blood donation followed by a subsequent HIV positive donation.</i>	American Red Cross Blood Centers of the Pacific South Africa National Blood Services (SANBS) Hemocentro do Sao Paulo	United States South Africa Brazil

Table 3: Demographic / infection characteristics of subjects contributing specimens to the evaluation panel

Subject/ specimen group	Number of subjects (% of subjects)	Number of specimens (% of specimens)
All subjects	928 (100)	2500 (100)
Gender		
Male	728 (78)	1872 (75)
Female	194 (21)	547 (22)
Country of specimen draws		
USA	523 (56)	1298 (52)
Zambia	166 (18)	508 (20)
Rwanda	65 (7)	281 (11)
Uganda	62 (7)	200 (8)
Brazil	18 (2)	85 (3)
South Africa	58 (6)	64 (3)
Kenya	36 (4)	63 (3)
Age at draw (years)		
<20	28 (3)	49 (2)
20-30	231 (25)	566 (23)
30-40	357 (38)	887 (35)
40-50	270 (29)	635 (25)
50-60	92 (10)	240 (10)
>60	21 (2)	45 (2)
HIV Subtype ¹		
B	525 (57)	1247 (50)
C	250 (27)	670 (27)
A1	92 (10)	290 (12)
D	42 (5)	157 (6)
Other	19 (2)	135 (5)

¹ 42% of subjects (capturing 52% of specimens) had their infection subtypes confirmed through laboratory testing, while the remainder of subtypes were based on the majority subtype in country of specimen draw.

Figure 1: Number of specimens drawn over time per subject, for specimens included on the evaluation panel

Table 4: Times from (estimated) infection to specimen draws for ARV-naïve subjects included in the evaluation panel (for estimation of the MDRI), stratified by HIV subtype¹

	All subtypes	Subtype B	Subtype C	Subtype A1	Subtype D
Subject/ specimen group	Number of subjects				
Subject has estimable infection date ²	422	104	185	83	38
<1 year duration of infection (DOI) at specimen draw	283	59	145	39	33
1-2 years DOI	224	39	105	54	19
2-3 years DOI	125	22	56	34	11
3-4 years DOI	72	15	33	19	4
4+ years DOI	41	14	19	7	0
Subject/ specimen group	Number of specimens				
Subject has estimable infection date ²	1386	344	588	263	149
<1 year duration of infection (DOI) at specimen draw	671	164	308	71	103
1-2 years DOI	346	70	146	93	27
2-3 years DOI	189	42	72	58	14
3-4 years DOI	104	28	40	29	4
4+ years DOI	66	34	20	11	0

¹ Elite controllers (defined in *Analysis of Assay Characteristics*) from SCOPE (see Table 2) are excluded as the study specifically recruited (untreated) subjects with sustained low HIV viral loads, and therefore data would otherwise be over-enriched with elite controllers.

² Infection refers to the time of positivity of Western blot. See *Analysis of Assay Characteristics* for the approach used for estimating infection times, and for identifying subjects with estimable infected times, for this particular analysis.

Table 5: Description of specimens from ARV-naïve long-infected subjects included in the evaluation panel (for estimation of the FRR), stratified by HIV subtype¹

	All subtypes	Subtype B	Subtype C	Subtype A1	Subtype D
Subject/ specimen group	Number of subjects				
Subject infected for greater than 1 year ²	456	243	121	62	21
Subject infected for greater than 2 years ²	316	190	75	37	11
Subject infected for greater than 3 years ²	224	156	42	20	4
Subject infected for greater than 4 years ²	161	137	18	6	0
Subject infected for greater than 5 years ²	111	111	0	0	0
Subject/ specimen group	Number of specimens				
Subject infected for greater than 1 year ²	1112	538	297	210	47
Subject infected for greater than 2 years ²	665	388	144	106	18
Subject infected for greater than 3 years ²	416	301	63	43	4
Subject infected for greater than 4 years ²	285	256	19	10	0
Subject infected for greater than 5 years ²	192	192	0	0	0

¹ Elite controllers (defined in *Analysis of Assay Characteristics*) from SCOPE (see Table 2) are excluded as the study specifically recruited (untreated) subjects with sustained low HIV viral loads, and therefore data would otherwise be over-enriched with elite controllers.

² Specimen drawn at least 1, 2, 3, 4 or 5 years (see row labels) after a first recorded HIV-positive diagnosis.

Table 6: Description of *challenge* specimens drawn from subjects infected for greater than 2 years included in the evaluation panel (for estimation of the FRR)¹

Subject/ specimen group	All subtypes ²	
	Number of subjects	Number of specimens
SCOPE elite controllers ²	31	89
CD4 cell count < 200 at draw	124	214
Treated subjects ³	113	185
Treatment initiated within 6 months of infection	53	90
Treatment initiated 6-24 months after infection	17	28
Treatment initiated >24 months after infection	33	54
Viral load < 75 copies/ml	154	273

¹ 98% of subjects (or specimens) represent subtype B infections.

² Subjects were identified as elite controllers by SCOPE (classification rules are outlined in defined in *Analysis of Assay Characteristics*).

³ Treated for at least 3 months and without interruption.

Analysis of Assay Characteristics

The methods and results outlined below are reported in the following journal article: ‘Kassanjee R, Pilcher CD, Keating SM, Facente SN, McKinney E, Price MA, Martin JN, Little S, Hecht FM, Kallas EG, Welte A, Busch MP, Murphy G, on behalf of the *Consortium for the Evaluation and Performance of HIV Incidence Assays* (CEPHIA); Independent assessment of candidate HIV incidence assays on specimens in the CEPHIA repository [3].

Definitions of Assay Characteristics

In 1995, Brookmeyer and Quinn [4] introduced the concept of cross-sectional HIV incidence estimation: incidence can be measured from a single survey conducted a point in time using both (i) observed survey counts of HIV-negative, ‘recently’ infected and ‘non-recently’ infected subjects, and (ii) knowledge about the dynamics of the test for recent infection. However, the state of ‘recent’ infection demonstrated in their work (namely, detectability of p24 antigens in the absence of detectable HIV antibodies) occurs for only a few weeks after infection, resulting in unrealistically large surveys being required for precise incidence estimation. Subsequently, various tests, with more enduring states of ‘recent’ infection, have been proposed. However, the behaviour of currently available tests has been imperfect – due to inter-subject variability, a substantial proportion of long-infected individuals nevertheless return ‘recent’ results.

As the methodology has matured, a general theoretical framework has been derived, which consistently accounts for these ‘false-recent’ results [5]. Two test characteristics that summarise test dynamics emerge as required for purposes of incidence surveillance:

- the **mean duration of recent infection (MDRI)**, Ω_T , which is the average time spent alive and ‘recently’ infected, while infected for less than some time cut-off T , and
- the **false-recent rate (FRR)**, β_T , which is the probability that an individual who is infected for longer than T will return a ‘recent’ result.

This general framework was developed by introducing a post-infection time cut-off, T , to separate ‘true-recent’ from ‘false-recent’ results. In a cross-sectional survey, the estimate of incidence would be

$$\hat{I}_T = \frac{n_R - \hat{\beta}_T n_+}{n_S \cdot (\hat{\Omega}_T - \hat{\beta}_T T)},$$

where n_+ and $n_S = n - n_+$ are the counts of HIV-positive and HIV-negative (or susceptible) subjects in the survey, n_R is the number of ‘recently’ infected subjects in the survey, and $\hat{\Omega}_T$ and $\hat{\beta}_T$ are the estimated MDRI and FRR for the test for recent infection respectively.

This analysis focuses on estimation of the MDRI and FRR. As the characteristics of incidence assays may vary across subpopulations, the characteristics are explored using various specimen sets.

Data Analysis Methods

Software. All data captured within CEPHIA are stored in a MySQL relational database. Database queries linked assay results to the background information on subjects and specimens for data analysis, which was then performed in Matlab (R2013b, the MathWorks Inc.).

Interpretation of assay results. The BED results were interpreted according to developer's guidelines (see standard operating procedures on the CEPHIA project website [1]). In particular, a 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold of 0.8 was used to discriminate between 'recent' and 'non-recent' infection, with a measured normalised optical density (ODn) of 0.8 or less interpreted as indicating 'recent' infection.

Stratification of data. Assay characteristics were estimated using specimen sets defined by stratifying on treatment history, viral load, CD4+ T cell count, time from infection to specimen draw, and HIV subtype (which was based on country of draw, for the 48% of specimens which lack explicit laboratory subtype confirmation). The characteristics of assays in 'elite controllers' (ECs), broadly defined as subjects who maintain undetectable or very low HIV viral loads without antiretroviral therapy (ART), is of particular interest. As the SCOPE study purposefully recruited ECs, this data was analysed separately. These subjects were ART-naïve (or without ART for at least 6 months), with all off-treatment viral load measurements (HIV-1 RNA) below 200 copies/ml and at least 50% of these measurements below 75 copies/ml.

Time cut-off T . The definitions of the MDRI and FRR rely on the previously mentioned construct of a post-infection time cut-off, T . If T is chosen to be too short, this limits the possible MDRI and typically raises the FRR. If T is chosen to be too long, it becomes difficult to obtain sufficient data to analyse the test dynamics with sufficient precision over this time after infection, and the MDRI will also develop variation by time and place (properties inevitable for the FRR) rather than capture stable biological properties of the test. A cut-off of $T = 2$ years is used throughout this work. The value of T was increased from 1 year, as used in preliminary analyses [2], to 2 years in this analysis, to better capture the tails of persisting 'recent' results and thus reduce FRRs.

Definition and estimation of infection times. In practice, the notion of 'infection' implicit in the assay characteristic definitions refers to 'detectable infection' – which depends on the particular HIV diagnostic test used in the incidence study. In this analysis, 'detectable infection' was defined as the time of seroconversion on an HIV viral lysate-based Western Blot assay. Based on the methodology summarised below, infection times were estimated for 56% of subjects.

The estimation of a subject's infection time relies on both data describing the subject's testing history and knowledge of the sensitivities of the various diagnostics tests used on the subject, where sensitivity captures the probability of detecting HIV in a (truly infected) subject as a function of time since detectability on the reference diagnostic test that is to be used in the incidence study (Western Blot in this case). In general, the formal likelihood of observing a subject's testing history can be directly generated as a function of time since

HIV infection (through vertical and horizontal inversion of the various diagnostic tests' sensitivity functions). Under prior assumptions about infection times, this likelihood function can then be used to produce an inferred posterior density function for possible infection times, which can then be used in analyses. Depending on available data, various simplifications of this estimation procedure could be considered.

For this analysis, infection times were estimated for subjects with available first HIV-positive test dates, Fiebig staging [6] information for first HIV-positive tests, and, at times, last HIV-negative test dates (within 120 days of first HIV-positive dates). The likelihood function for the infection time (corresponding to the time of entering Fiebig stage 5) of a subject was then calculated using the average durations of Fiebig stages presented in Lee et al [7] (neglecting inter-subject variability, assuming independence between diagnostic results for a subject, and making some assumptions about the types of diagnostics tests used at last HIV-negative test dates). A uniform prior for infection times was combined with the likelihood function, and the mean of the resulting posterior distribution for infection times provided a subject's estimated infection time, which was used in all subsequent analyses.

Efforts are currently being made to capture more detailed information on cohort-level diagnostic testing protocols and more complete testing histories of individual subjects, thus providing the required data to refine estimation of infection times for later analyses of assay results.

For subjects with unambiguous acute retroviral syndrome (ARS) symptoms onset dates between last HIV-negative and first HIV-positive test dates, infection was estimated to occur 17 days after ARS onset (based on the observation that the incubation period of ARS symptoms is about 14 days [8-11] and that the time from exposure to Western blot seroconversion averages 31 days [6,7]).

Estimation of MDRI. A number of methods can reasonably be used to estimate the MDRI, each with its own accuracy, precision and complexity – as explored in a separate, detailed benchmarking exercise (manuscript in preparation, by a working group operating on behalf of the HIV Modelling Consortium [12]). In this analysis, linear binomial regression, an approach found to be robust across a number of scenarios in this benchmarking project, and previously used for this purpose [13], has been applied. The model form is $g(P_R(t)) = f(t)$ where $P_R(t)$ is the probability of testing 'recent' at time t after infection, g is the chosen link function and $f(t)$ is a linear function of the model parameters, which are estimated by a maximum likelihood approach. Results from a 4-parameter model form are presented, where g is the logit link, and $f(t)$ is a cubic polynomial in t (Model A). Data points more than $1.1 \times T$ post infection were discarded before model fitting (Data Exclusion Rule I), with the aim of achieving the best fit of the model over $[0, T]$ post-infection, while avoiding diluting the data around the boundary at T . Sensitivity of results when increasing the data exclusion cut-off to $2 \times T$ (Data Exclusion Rule II) was also considered. Variation in results was explored when fitting two other model forms, namely (i) a more restrictive 2-parameter model where g is the log-log link and $f(t)$ is a linear function of $\ln(t)$ (Model B), and (ii) a flexible 7-parameter model where g is the logit link and $f(t)$ is a linear function of the natural cubic spline basis functions with interior knots occurring every 3 months after

infection, between 0 and T after infection (Model C). In all cases, the MDRI, expressed mathematically as $\int_0^T P_R(t)dt$, was estimated using the fitted $P_R(t) = g^{-1}(f(t))$.

To correctly account for the structure of the data, in the absence of explicit subject-level clustering in the fitted models, bootstrapping was performed by sampling subjects (not observations) with replacement. The 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of 10 000 MDRI estimate replicates provided 95% confidence interval (CI) limits [14].

Estimation of FRR. A population-level FRR is inherently dependent on the epidemiological and demographic history of a study population, and so a set of specimens, such as in the CEPHIA repository, can only be used to estimate the FRR in well-defined subpopulations. Therefore, specimens from long-infected subjects were identified (specimens drawn at least T after the subject's first recorded HIV-positive test time – adjusted to capture Western blot positivity), and the proportion of 'recently' infected subjects estimated in each of the specimen sets described above. To capture subject-level clustering, when a subject provided more than one result to any FRR estimate, the most frequent classification was used. When a subject had equal numbers of 'recent' and 'non-recent' classifications, the subject contributed 0.5 to the count of subjects who have a majority 'recent' classification. Exact Clopper-Pearson 95% CIs [15] are provided.

Reproducibility statistics. The sample mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation of the multiple assay measurements obtained for each of the unique reproducibility specimens, as well as each of the labelled quality controls, were also calculated.

Results

The incidence assay dynamics, excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers, are shown in Figures 2 to 4. The evolution of assay measurements by time since infection is shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3. In Figure 4, the proportion of ‘recent’ results (assay measurements below the ‘recent’/‘non-recent’ threshold) is plotted by time since infection, also stratified by HIV subtype (B, C, D, and A1). The figures show that there is natural variability in biomarker maturation, leading to a significant number of subjects reaching the standard ‘recent’/‘non-recent’ threshold more than one year after infection; and there is significant delay or failure to achieve maturation to ‘non-recent’ status among specimens of subtype A1 and D.

The distribution of assay measurements for specimens drawn more than $T = 2$ years after infection is shown in Figure 5, for various specimen sets.

Figure 2: Spaghetti plot of subjects’ assay measurements as a function of (estimated) time since infection (years), excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers

The figure represents 1376 data points from 418 subjects. The ‘recent’/‘non-recent’ threshold is shown by a horizontal solid line.

Figure 3: Box-and-whisker plots of assay measurements as a function of (estimated) time since infection (years), excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers

The plot indicates percentiles of measurements in 6-monthly intervals of time after infection. The central 50% and median of measurements are captured by the box and dividing line respectively, and whiskers and markers capture remaining measurements and outliers respectively. There are 40-450 data points per group. The 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold is shown by the horizontal solid line.

Figure 4: The proportion of 'recent' results (%) as a function of (estimated) time since infection (years), excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers and stratifying by HIV subtype (B, C, D and A1)

Circles and lines show observed proportions and 95% confidence intervals respectively. Specimens are grouped into 6-monthly intervals of time since infection until 2 years, after which all specimens are grouped together. There are 25 to 665 data points per group, except for subtype D which has fewer than 20 points 1-2 years after infection.

A. All subtypes

B. Subtype B

C. Subtype C

D. Subtype D

E. Subtype A1

Figure 5: Empirical distribution of assay measurements for specimens drawn greater than $T = 2$ years after (estimated) infection time, by specimen set
 'Recent'/'non-recent' thresholds are shown by vertical solid lines.

A. Excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers

665 data points from 316 subjects.

B. Treated subjects

Treated for at least 3 months without interruption. 185 data points from 113 subjects.

C. SCOPE elite controllers

89 data points from 31 subjects.

D. Low viral load

Viral load < 75 copies/ml at draw. 273 data points from 154 subjects.

E. Low CD4+ T cell count

CD4 cell count < 200 cells/ μ l at draw. 214 data points from 124 subjects.

Table 7 provides estimated assay characteristics for various specimen sets. The estimated MDRI, excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers from the analysis, is 302 days (95% CI: 274-331). The result was insensitive (less than 1% change in result) to whether ARS symptoms onset dates were used to adjust estimated infection dates, a change to Data Exclusion Rule II, and the use of alternative Model C. The MDRI estimate increased by 3% when changing to Model B, which was the most sensitive to the data exclusion rules (5% increase in estimate when changing to Data Exclusion Rule II within Model B).

While characteristics have been estimated here on the standardized basis of a Western blot being used to identify HIV-positive subjects, other diagnostic screening tests are likely to be used in incidence studies, and the time between HIV exposure and reactivity on these tests can differ by several weeks [6,7,16]. Therefore, for application to incidence studies, the base case MDRI reported here would need to be increased or decreased – depending on the particular screening test or algorithm used in the study to classify a specimen as HIV-positive, and hence eligible for ‘recent’ infection testing.

The estimated FRRs provided in Table 7 are also plotted in Figure 6. Excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers, and analysing all remaining specimens drawn more than $T = 2$ years after infection, the measured FRR is 7.4% (95% CI: 4.8%-10.9%). When stratifying by time since infection, persistence of ‘recent’ classifications is evident.

The FRR amongst elite controller specimens is high at 19% (95% CI: 7%-38%). The FRR amongst treated subjects is even higher, at 66% (95% CI: 56%-75%). Further stratifying treated subjects by time from infection to treatment initiation, the FRR decreases as the time to treatment initiation increases: for early treatment initiation (within 6 months of infection) the FRR is 87% (95% CI: 74%-95%), while for later treatment initiation (more than 6 months after infection) it is 41% (95% CI: 27%-55%).

The FRR for subjects with low viral loads, here defined as below 75 copies/ml, is high, at 57% (95% CI: 48%-65%). This is consistent with results above, as 92% of this specimen set is made up of specimens from the identified elite controllers and treated subjects (and 94% of specimens from SCOPE elite controllers and treated subjects have a low viral load).

The FRR amongst subjects with low CD4+ T cell counts, namely less than 200 cells/ μ l and acting as a proxy for AIDS identification, was relatively low at 4% (95% CI: 1%-10%).

Table 8 lists MDRI and FRR by subtype. Small p-values for pairwise subtype differences in the MDRI or FRRs involve subtype A1 versus B, and there are at times large differences between MDRI and FRR point estimates when comparing subtypes. While these initial results highlight potential subtype differences and support further exploration of this topic, a more definitive analysis (beyond the present scope) should be performed – based on a large number of subtype D and A1 specimens and using estimation procedures specifically adapted to this stratification.

Table 7: Estimated assay characteristics (and 95% confidence intervals), for various specimen sets

Assay characteristics are estimated for $T = 2$ years and a context in which an HIV viral lysate-based Western blot assay is used to identify HIV-positive subjects in the incidence study.

	Number of subjects (number of data points)	Estimated assay characteristics (95% CI)
MDRI in days		
All specimens, excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers	400 (1032)	302 (274-331)
FRR as %		
All specimens, excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers	316 (665)	7.4 (4.8-10.9)
By time since infection (years), excluding treated subjects and SCOPE elite controllers		
(2,3]	140 (208)	12.5 (7.5-19.1)
(3,4]	77 (110)	7.1 (2.5-15.4)
(4,5]	35 (45)	7.1 (1.2-21.1)
>5	112 (193)	6.7 (2.8-13.0)
Elite controllers (identified by SCOPE cohort)	31 (89)	19.4 (7.5-37.5)
Treated subjects (no previous treatment interruption and treated for at least 3 months)	113 (185)	65.9 (56.4-74.6)
By time from infection to treatment (years)		
[0,0.5)	53 (90)	86.8 (74.7-94.5)
≥0.5	53 (88)	40.6 (27.3-54.9)
Low viral load (<75 copies/ml at draw)	154 (273)	56.5 (48.3-64.5)
Low CD4+ T cell count (<200 cells/μl at draw)	124 (214)	4.0 (1.3-9.2)

Figure 6: Estimated proportions of 'recent' results in various sets of specimens drawn from subjects infected for greater than $T=2$ years

Table 8: Estimated assay characteristics (and 95% confidence intervals), for ARV-naïve subjects and excluding SCOPE elite controllers, by subtype

Assay characteristics are estimated for $T = 2$ years and a context in which an HIV viral lysate-based Western blot assay is used to identify HIV-positive subjects in the incidence study.

	Number of subjects (number of data points)	Estimated assay characteristics (95% CI)
MDRI in days¹		
All specimens	400 (1032)	302 (274-331)
Subtype B	90 (246)	255 (208-308)
Subtype C	181 (454)	287 (248-328)
Subtype D	38 (131)	328 (227-433)
Subtype A1	80 (166)	363 (288-442)
FRR as %²		
All specimens	316 (665)	7.4 (4.8-10.9)
Subtype B	190 (388)	4.7 (2.2-8.8)
Subtype C	75 (144)	7.3 (2.6-15.7)
Subtype D	11 (18)	18.2 (2.3-51.8)
Subtype A1	37 (106)	18.9 (8.0-35.2)

¹ In a test for pairwise differences in MDRI by subtype, using a z-test, the following pairs provided p-values below 0.05: A1&B. Estimated standard deviations of the MDRI estimators are used as proxies for true values, and therefore tests are anticonservative (particularly when sample sizes are small).

² In a test for pairwise differences in FRRs by subtype, using the Fisher-Boschloo test [17], the following pairs provided p-values below 0.05: A1&B.

Lastly, Figures 7 and 8 summarise the assay measurements for the reproducibility of CEPHIA control specimens included in the evaluation. 75 of the uniquely-labelled 2 500 specimens on the evaluation panel represent 25 aliquots of each of three underlying specimens. The reproducibility of measurements for these 3 ‘blinded’ controls is described in Figure 7. Four labelled CEPHIA internal quality controls were also tested regularly during evaluation panel testing, for confirmation of stability of the assay. The results for these controls are summarised in Figure 8.

Figure 7: Reproducibility of CEPHIA *unlabelled* controls

The box-and-whisker plots (top) provide percentiles of the 25 measurements for each of the three blinded reproducibility specimens (labelled A, B and C in the figure only). The central 50% and median of measurements are captured by the box and dividing line respectively, and whiskers and markers capture remaining measurements and outliers respectively. The 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold is shown by the vertical solid line. The observed reproducibility statistics (mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation) of measurements are also tabulated (bottom).

Summary of measurements				
Specimen identifier	Number of measurements	Mean (ODn)	Standard deviation (ODn)	Coefficient of variation (%)
A	25	0.4	0.1	18
B	25	2.9	0.3	9
C	25	3.8	0.2	6

Figure 8: Reproducibility of CEPHIA labelled controls

The box-and-whisker plots (top) provide percentiles of the 14-106 measurements for each of the four labelled quality control specimens (labelled D, E, F and G in the figure only). The central 50% and median of measurements are captured by the box and dividing line respectively, and whiskers and markers capture remaining measurements and outliers respectively. The 'recent'/'non-recent' threshold is shown by the vertical solid line. The observed reproducibility statistics (mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation) of measurements are also tabulated (bottom).

Summary of measurements				
Specimen identifier	Number of measurements	Mean (ODn)	Standard deviation (ODn)	Coefficient of variation (%)
D	92	0.1	0.03	38
E	14	0.1	0.03	23
F	106	0.7	0.1	8
G	106	2.8	0.2	9

Conclusion/Recommendations

The following conclusions relate to the SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA assay :

- 1) The SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA is a robustly reproducible assay that is easily deployed with technical ease. The assay is affordable and does not require significant additional laboratory equipment outside of that which could be reasonably expected.
- 2) However, given its performance in relation to the Target Product Profile, and to other candidate assays currently available, CEPHIA does not recommend it for use in cross-sectional incidence assays.
- 3) Although the assay does have dynamic range in which it can identify recent infection, CEPHIA feel that the false recent rate found in the evaluation of the assay does not make it a promising candidate for future widespread use.
- 4) A number of groups are looking at alternative uses for HIV Incidence assays and the potential exists that the assay may be better suited for some alternative uses. However, the CEPHIA group do not believe that varying of thresholds or application of currently described RITA algorithms will improve the performance of this assay to an acceptable level to support its inclusion cross sectional incidence studies. Evaluation of this assay against other TPPs will be performed when these are published.
- 5) CEPHIA has been led to believe that this assay may undergo a change in antigen at some time in the future. This may change the performance of the assay which CEPHIA is unable to evaluate. Should a change in antigen occur then this evaluation of the assay will no longer be relevant.

Technical Appraisal

Assay Kits and Reagents

The SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA is comprised of two component boxes that have **separate** temperature requirements. This means both a fridge and freezer are required at the test site to correctly store this assay. The Freezer Pack (3013) and the Refrigerator Pack (3012) have matching lot numbers and it is **critical** that only matching lot numbers are used together during testing.

The 10X Wash Buffer Concentrate is lot number independent and so can be used with other kit lots and with the SEDIA™ HIV-1 LAg-Avidity EIA (Cat No. 1002). This is helpful as the 1X Wash Buffer can be stored at 2-30°C for up to one month in which time kit lots may have changed.

The kit contains two 96-well plates with twelve (12 1 x 8 removable strips which may be broken down further into individual wells to be inserted back into the plate frame so that only exact number of wells need to be used. This reduces waste of wells and hence cost, however this may cause problems if the plate washer in use cannot be programmed on an individual well/strip basis. In this case empty spaces in the plate frame must be filled. Each test plate requires 11 wells be allocated for the controls and calibrators, thus in the initial screening mode, up to 85 specimens can be tested, and in the confirmatory mode up to 28 specimens can be tested in triplicate. (See Appendix 2 for recommended plate configurations)

Each kit contains all the necessary reagents to run the assay. The bottles are well labelled and easily identifiable.

Equipment

Most of the equipment and materials required but not provided are standard laboratory pieces and should not pose a problem for a testing laboratory. Further details on some items are described below:

Plate washing:

Test plates are washed 4 times (rotating the plate after the first 2 washes) with 1x wash Buffer using a 96-well, or strip washer. The washer is set to dispense 300µl/well with a 10-second soak. Soaking is not required if a strip washer is used. This is a standard wash programme and should not pose a problem for testing laboratories.

Positive displacement pipette or microliter syringe:

The “recommended” use of a positive displacement or microliter syringe to prepare the Conjugate Working Solution was added to version 3 of the Kit insert.

25°C Incubator:

SEDIA require the use of a second incubator during the TMB substrate incubation. Some laboratories have identified to CEPHIA that they may find this an issue.

Associated documentation

The availability, usability and reliability of accompanying documents e.g spreadsheets, worksheets, data files, kit inserts, QC charts, is vital to the performance of the assay. The user is reliant on the Developer/Manufacturer to ensure formatting, formulas and information is correct and available in any such documents.

There are two associated documents with the SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA

1. Kit Insert

Printed Kit inserts are supplied with each Assay Kit detailing the test procedure, run validation and calculation and interpretation of results. Kit inserts are clearly presented and contain all relevant detail to perform the assay correctly.

2. BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA Data Management Worksheet

The SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA is intended to be used with a customized spreadsheet which is used to validate the run and calculates ODn values. The SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA Data Management Worksheet is provided by the manufacturer, SEDIA, and is available on their website for use by any laboratory using the BED Assay http://www.hivincidence.com/BED_HIV-1_Incidence_EIA.html

This spreadsheet was used throughout the CEPHIA evaluation to validate test runs and compile data. The cut-off values for the kit controls did not alter between kit lots and remained consistent on the data management file.

ACCEPTABLE OD RANGES FROM BED DATA MANAGEMENT FILE SPREADSHEET (SEDIA WEBSITE)

Acceptable Ranges				
	NC	CAL	LPC	HPC
OD	0.000	0.380	0.200	0.600
	0.250	1.350	0.800	2.100
ODn	0.000	1.000	0.400	1.200
	0.300	1.000	0.750	1.900

FROM BED KIT INSERT (VERSION 1):

	NC	CAL	LPC	HPC
Minimum	0.000	0.380	0.200	0.600
Maximum	0.250	1.350	0.800	2.100

FROM BED KIT INSERT (VERSION 4):

	NC	CAL	LPC	HPC
Minimum	0.000	0.380	0.200	0.600
Maximum	0.250	1.350	0.800	2.100

ISSUE 1: Negative OD values

The Kit insert states that both individual OD values for the Negative Control must be within the stated range for the assay to pass. However, the original data management spreadsheet only based run validity on the median of the Negative OD values. The spreadsheet should include the full assay criteria as users may not manually verify both negative values when a VALID result appears on the spreadsheet.

This issue was rectified by the manufacturer and customers were made aware on 27th February 2013 (please note that this is after the testing of the Evaluation Panel was complete).

ISSUE 2: Control ODn values

The Data Management File spreadsheet does not take into account the validity of the kit Control **ODn** values. The kit insert gives acceptable ranges for both OD and ODn values. However, the spreadsheet bases run validity on OD values only. This can be misleading when a VALID result appears on the spreadsheet, as users may not also manually evaluate the control ODn values to ensure they are within acceptable ranges.

The OD values being in the acceptable range does not necessarily mean the ODn values are within range. If both OD and ODn are to be within acceptable ranges the spreadsheet should reflect this in its VALID/INVALID interpretation.

This issue was rectified by the manufacturer and customers were made aware on 27th February 2013 (please note that this is after the testing of the Evaluation Panel was complete).

Technical Conclusions

The manufacturer was informed of the issues with the **LAg-Avidity EIA Data Management Worksheet** via a CEPHIA report on 29/11/2012. Similar issues were found on the **BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA Data Management Worksheet** as detailed above. CEPHIA was informed that the spreadsheet(s) were being updated and would be available soon. Up until this time the original spreadsheet with errors was still supplied on the website for use by kit users. From a user perspective the continued supply of incorrect documentation and hence the low quality data that results from this is disappointing and frustrating. From an evaluation perspective it also raises concerns that other users are unaware of the errors within the spreadsheet and as such will have incorrect data.

The website was updated with a new spreadsheet (Version LN-6083) in February 2013, which had a number of amendments:

- Requirement for laboratory Plate reader Limit of Detection was added
- The Valid/Invalid criteria is based on the individual OD values for the negative control
- Both the OD and ODn values for the kit controls have to be within acceptable ranges to be deemed VALID

CEPHIA appreciates that as assays develop there will be changes to ranges and documentation but recommends that a comprehensive method of informing users of changes should be employed as well as vigorous checking of spreadsheets containing formulae.

Target Product Profile performance

Specification	Acceptable Performance	Ideal Performance	How does BED fit?
<i>Intended Use</i>	<i>Population-based incidence estimate</i>	<i>Population-based incidence estimate, prevention-trial planning, community-level prevention intervention studies</i>	<i>Although it has a long recency period, it has a high false recent rate. Not appropriate for solo use in incidence calculations</i>
<i>Target Population</i>	<i>Specific to clade</i>	<i>All clades</i>	<i>Performance of non-clade B is worse than clade B. Not appropriate for international population based incidence surveillance.</i>
<i>False Recent Rate (FRR)</i>	<i>Confidently measured to be less than 2% in different populations (with different clades, epidemic phases, treatment coverage etc)</i>	<i>0% in all population (No evidence of false-recent classifications).</i>	<i>7% - Failed</i>
<i>Mean Duration</i>	<i>4 months (95% CI, +/- 0.2)</i>	<i>1 year (95% CI, +/- 0.2)</i>	<i>302 days - Acceptable</i>
<i>Algorithm</i>	<i>Included in a RITA</i>	<i>None required</i>	<i>CEPHIA does not recommend use of this assay</i>
<i>Analyte</i>	<i>Any</i>	<i>Any</i>	<i>Anti-HIV-1 antibodies</i>
<i>sample Type</i>	<i>Frozen serum, frozen plasma</i>	<i>Frozen serum or plasma , dried blood spots (or other easily obtained and stored sample)</i>	<i>Frozen serum or plasma/DBS available - Ideal</i>
<i>Sample Volume</i>	<i>1 mL</i>	<i>10 uL or fingerstick</i>	<i>Acceptable - 40uL total.</i>

Infrastructure requirements	Centralized laboratory facility (clean water and electricity available)	None (all reagents and necessary materials to run assay are in self-contained kit)	Acceptable -Centralized Lab.
Storage/Shipping Conditions	4-25 °C	Ambient temperature	Failed -4°C and -25 °C
Incubation Temperature	4-25 °C	Ambient temperature	Failed - 25°C and 37 °C
Shelf Life	9 months	>18 months	Ideal ->18 months ideal
Training	Laboratory technician can be proficient with one week's training based on proficiency testing	Minimal training would allow any health worker to conduct the assay	Acceptable -Laboratory technician can be proficient with one week's training based on proficiency testing
Regulatory Pathway	GMP or ISO 13485 or equivalent, and/or approval by national governing body	FDA and equivalents	Manufactured in GMP facility – approved by CDC.

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Appendix

1. Evaluation Protocol

Background

The SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA is to be evaluated by the CEPHIA group as part of The Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded project, 'Development of specimen repository and evaluation of assays for identification of recent HIV infection and estimation of HIV incidence'. The group will also undertake evaluations of a number of other available assays for HIV recency. Each of these evaluations will have their own CEPHIA Book Report available.

Evaluation Purpose

To advance the understanding of currently available assays that can identify recent HIV infection; to better describe the duration of the infection state in which they identify recent infection; and to determine the rate at which they misclassify specimens as from recent infections

Conduct of the evaluation

All CEPHIA evaluations are conducted following the **CEPHIA Quality Management Strategy** (Document 002) which details the quality planning, quality control and quality assurance in place at Public Health England (PHE), Microbiology Services (MS), Colindale and the collaborating organisations of Blood Systems Research Institute (BSRI), San Francisco, University of California, San Francisco (UCSF) and South African Centre for Epidemiological Modelling and Analysis (SACEMA), University of Stellenbosch, South Africa, to ensure the delivery of the Bill & Melinda Gates Funded (BMGF) Project.

The main objectives of the quality strategy are: to define the quality requirements, how they are to be met, who is responsible for meeting requirements, and helping to align quality strategies between the multiple sites involved in the overall project.

The CEPHIA Quality Management Strategy details the quality procedures in place for all CEPHIA evaluations with regards to Project Organisation – roles, responsibilities and personnel, Facilities, Equipment, Standard Operating procedures (SOP), Worksheets, Plans, Sub-contracting, Conduct of project, Computer systems, Safety and risk, Method validations, Results, Reporting process and templates, Repeat analysis, Retention of data/specimens, Confidentiality. The quality strategy will be based on UK CPA standards and also MHRA Good Clinical Practise 'Guidance on the maintenance of regulatory compliance in laboratories that perform the analysis or evaluation of clinical trial samples', it will also refer to local site regulations and standards.

- **The assay under evaluation will be tested in exactly the manner described in the manufacturer/developers instructions.**
- **Evaluator(s) will strictly adhere to the quality requirements laid out in the CEPHIA Quality Management Strategy.**
- **Prior to beginning the evaluation, the manufacturer/developer will be invited, if they so wish, to provide training to the evaluator in the use of the assay kit and equipment and to satisfy themselves that the evaluator(s) is trained sufficiently.**

Specimen Handling

A main objective of this project is to compile large-volume, standardized sample sets appropriate for comparative evaluation of tests for recent HIV infection in an accessible central repository.

These serum samples will be sourced by the CEPHIA team at University of California San Francisco (UCSF), blinded so evaluator(s) will not know the expected results, then aliquotted at the central repository (Blood Systems Research Institute, San Francisco) and shipped to the relevant test site.

Documentation

The CEPHIA group have compiled a folder of documents relating to the plans, procedures and protocols required for the high quality performance and completion of the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation funded project. These documents are securely stored in a management-only access folder until the project end. Some relevant documents are available for public reading on the CEPHIA website at <http://www.incidence-estimation.com/archivesuploads/index/NAME/11>

Other aspects of the evaluation

Technical appraisal of the procedure, assay kit and equipment required for the performance of the assay. This may include ease of use, reliability, packaging, clarity, health and safety considerations.

Discordant results

A discrepancy may arise at the test site and should be investigated by an appropriately trained person prior to data being verified and reported for analysis. If a discrepancy is identified at the analysis site (SACEMA), a report detailing the error will be sent to the test site for further investigation.

Analysis of results and evaluation report

The raw laboratory data is compiled and verified at the test site. It is stored electronically in a Data Table formatted as described in the *CEPHIA Data Processing Protocol: Data Flow, Recording and Standard Formats*.

Verified and formatted data is e-mailed to the analysis site (SACEMA). The analysis site will run data through checks and generate a report prior to using the data for analysis. Data analysis will be reported in the CEPHIA Book. The manufacturer/developer of the assay concerned will be given the opportunity to comment on results prior to any publishing of data.

2. CEPHIA Project Management Contact Details

1. PHE – Public Health England, Microbiology Services, Colindale, London, UK
2. BSRI - Blood Systems Research Institute, San Francisco
3. UCSF – University of California, San Francisco
4. SACEMA - South African Centre for Epidemiological Modelling and Analysis

Project Management Team:				
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3. Recommended Test plate configurations

Screening plate diagram

NC	HPC	6	14	22	30	38	46	54	62	70	78
NC	HPC	7	15	23	31	39	47	55	63	71	79
CAL	HPC	8	16	24	32	40	48	56	64	72	80
CAL	1	9	17	25	33	41	49	57	65	73	81
CAL	2	10	18	26	34	42	50	58	66	74	82
LPC	3	11	19	27	35	43	51	59	67	75	83
LPC	4	12	20	28	36	44	52	60	68	76	84
LPC	5	13	21	29	37	45	53	61	69	77	85

Confirmatory plate diagram

NC	HPC	2	5	8	10	13	16	18	21	24	26
NC	HPC	3	5	8	11	13	16	19	21	24	27
CAL	HPC	3	6	8	11	14	16	19	22	24	27
CAL	1	3	6	9	11	14	17	19	22	25	27
CAL	1	4	6	9	12	14	17	20	22	25	28
LPC	1	4	7	9	12	15	17	20	23	25	28
LPC	2	4	7	10	12	15	18	20	23	26	28
LPC	2	5	7	10	13	15	18	21	23	26	BL*

Contact details for manufacturer

Sedia Biosciences Corporation
 Portland, Oregon USA
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 E-mail: customerservice@sedbio.com
 Web: www.sediabio.com

Manufacturer's comments

An early draft copy of this report was provided to Sedia. Following their review the CEPHIA management group reviewed the report and a number of changes were made. These mainly related to factual inaccuracies and clarifications of a number of points. Following this review a further copy of the report was provided to Sedia and their comments on this report are shown below. The CEPHIA management group wish to acknowledge, with thanks, the efforts Sedia have made in their comprehensive review of our report. As alerted to Sedia, a small number of corrections were made to the version that Sedia received as part of a final proof read.

Sedia Biosciences' Manufacturer's Response to CEPHIA Evaluation Report on Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA.

CEPHIA Report Dated 26 January 2015; Received by Sedia 03 February 2015

Manufacturer's Overview:

CEPHIA has graciously provided its Evaluation Report on the Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA for Sedia Biosciences' ("Sedia") comments which are included below. Sedia understands and appreciates the challenges in evaluating HIV Incidence Assays in a fair and unbiased way. From an industry standpoint, development of such assays present their own unique challenges. The market size for such products is currently very small, the evaluation of the developed assay, both during development and as final validation of the assay, require specimens not readily available except at considerable cost, and only limited funding either within or outside of industry is available for the pursuit of such assays.

Sedia is concerned that the structure of these reports appears to be a binary recommend/not recommend conclusion, without adequate consideration to other options that are practically available today, based on its reading of this report and the similar CEPHIA report of the Sedia™ HIV-1 LAg-Avidity EIA. From a potential user's perspective, an evaluation of all currently available incidence assays concluding that none can be recommended is of limited benefit to the user who does not have the resources to conduct a longitudinal cohort study but must rely on "the best assay" for the intended use that the user requires. A "Not Recommended" conclusion suggests an assay is without value, a position we believe many of our customers would not agree with.

The format of the evaluation also does not appear to take into account the effect of using an unmodified assay whose manufactured intent is for use as an incidence assay, versus using an assay manufactured and intended for diagnostic use but modified by a research lab or third party for use as an incidence assay. As both an incidence assay and a diagnostic assay manufacturer, Sedia appreciates that incidence assays are developed and qualified, manufacturing and raw materials changes made, by considering the impact to the assay's use for estimating incidence, as part of the manufacture of such an assay under GMPs. Similarly, a diagnostic assay is developed, qualified, manufacturing and raw materials changes made, by considering the impact to the assay's use as a diagnostic assay, not as an incidence assay. The end user of a diagnostic assay modified to be used for incidence estimation has no knowledge if the assay has been changed since initial evaluations have

been performed to establish MDRI and FRR values, and thus has no idea as to whether these critical values apply to the lot of product they are modifying and using. Sedia's experience is that incidence assays are more challenging to manufacture and qualify than diagnostic assays, and for good reason. There are more controls and data analysis to determine the performance of an incidence assay to be qualified for product release.

Specific issues and concerns about the report provided by CEPHIA are listed below:

Summary:

Data Analysis

Key assay characteristics determined by CEPHIA and reported in the Evaluation Report varied significantly from those determined by U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Evaluation, Atlanta (U.S. CDC) and published previously in peer-reviewed journals (notably MDRI and FRR values). Both the labs in CEPHIA and those at the U.S. CDC are well respected labs and the discrepancy between the results obtained is not addressed in the report and may be a reflection of the specimen populations evaluated.

Conclusions

The CEPHIA report has determined that the Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence Assay cannot be recommended based on the fact that the product does not reach the Target Product Profile (TPP) for use in cross sectional incidence assays. Sedia is unaware of any reported or published studies in which there is any HIV-1 incidence assay that reaches the TPP. The BED EIA is the first assay developed specifically for estimation of HIV-1 incidence, and is one of very few that do not use an adaptation of an assay which is designed for diagnostic use. Such assays are not controlled, regulated or validated relative to HIV-1 incidence measurement, a relatively small market, given the greater market demands typical for diagnostic use. The technology is also 14 years old, and Sedia acknowledges that improved assays (notably the Sedia™ HIV-1 LAg-Avidity EIA) may be more suitable. However, many of Sedia's customers have preferred to continue testing with the BED EIA, since lower False Recency Rates, good correlation with independent incidence assessments and a targeted population more consistent with the guidelines established by the CDC for use with the BED EIA enable them to track long term trends without shifting to a new assay.

Such applications justify the continued availability of the BED EIA, and supports Sedia's contention that there are still practical applications for the assay. In general, the absence of any assay conforming to the TPP, although a commendable goal, but therefore not "Recommended" rating provides little practical value to researchers who need some tool however less than ideal, to conduct incidence surveys, without resorting to more burdensome longitudinal cohort studies.

Introduction

The authors state that "Full evaluation of the Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA was considered justified following review of the qualification panel data by the CEPHIA management team and due to its previous widespread use in a number of studies." However the specific criteria for inclusion or exclusion of assays based on this review is not

described in the report, nor is any complete listing of assays excluded and included for “full evaluation” provided.

SEDIA™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA Information

As noted by the authors, the assay kit(s) evaluated were those available in 2013. Ongoing continuous product improvement is conducted to improve product consistency, manufacturability and performance in general, although internal target specifications (typically more extensive and constraining than the validity ranges followed by the end user) have changed minimally to ensure the product performs consistently with previous lots specifically for HIV incidence testing. These improvements continue today.

It should be noted that the BED EIA is the first commercial assay that was developed and designed specifically for estimating HIV-1 incidence, as opposed to adapting an assay manufactured, tested and released for the purposes solely of HIV diagnosis. As such, each lot of the product manufactured is tested and verified specifically for performance as an incidence assay, first internally, and then by the CDC. Sedia feels this is a significant advantage over other “adapted diagnostic assays” which may undergo changes or deviations by the manufacturer without verify the impact an unknowing end-user may experience when applying the assay to incidence estimation.

Table 1: Assay Information Summary

The following item is incorrect:

- Positive displacement pipette or microliter syringe capable of delivering 5-20 µL Should state “Recommended”, not “Required” (to improve accuracy and reduce likelihood of results falling out of the validity ranges)

Evaluation Panel and Method

Note that the kits used for evaluation cited in this section (Lots DA1201 and DH2401) were both approved and released in early and mid 2012 and respectively expired in mid and late 2013.

Table 3: Demographic / infection characteristics of subjects contributing specimens to the evaluation panel.

The subtype distribution in this report is more heavily skewed towards subtype B and C subjects than the data reported in the BED EIA insert that was generated by the Centers for Disease Control (CDC). In addition, only 42% of the subjects in the CEPHIA evaluation have confirmed subtypes, with the rest presumed to be the most common serotype of the country of the subject’s origin, which may or may not be the case. This may potentially impact the data related to assay performance relative to subtype if these are included in subtype analysis and therefore the authors’ conclusions about subtype specific performance of the assay. It is unclear whether subjects with unverified subtype were excluded from the subtype-related data analysis.

Analysis of Assay Characteristics

Results – Figures 2 and 3

The data in Figure 2 is of limited value as the assay is not intended to estimate time of infection, but to simply differentiate recent versus long-term infections relative to a single point, the MDRI (ω =197 days [95% CI 173-220] as determined by the CDC). To this end, it would be more valuable to assess time since infection relative to the cutoff (OD_n=0.8) in a scatter plot with quadrants demarcated by a vertical line at the MDRI (197 days) and a horizontal line at the cutoff (OD_n=0.8), and assessing the relative distribution in each quadrant of data points. The lines on the present figure obfuscate this information that correlates to the intended use of the assay. Similarly, data in Figure 3 reported out 1 or 2 years or more is of limited value except to the extent that data points are reported as false recent (i.e. falling into the lower right quadrant).

Table 7

The calculated MDRI (mean duration of recent infection) is longer in this report (302 days, 95% CI: 274-331) than that calculated by the CDC for the BED EIA (197 days, 95% CI 173-220). There could be multiple factors causing this. Sedia understands that CDC data is based on exclusion of individuals likely to be misclassified including recipients of antiretroviral therapy and elite controllers (excluded by the authors in their calculations) but also persons with diagnosis of AIDS or low CD4+ T cell counts, which the kit insert also advises should be excluded (see Limitations of the Assay). It's not clear if these latter individuals were also excluded from the analysis conducted by CEPHIA. Additionally, the effect due to differences in subtype distribution from the CDC population cited in the kit insert, as discussed above, potentially has an impact. A longer MDRI calculated by the authors compared to that calculated by the CDC also will likely increase the calculated FRR (false recency rate). The differences between reported FRR attributable to the difference in calculated MDRI cannot be determined from the data provided in this report.

Conclusion/Recommendations

Specific conclusions:

- 1) N/A
- 2) The second conclusion implies that since the Sedia™ HIV-1 BED Incidence EIA is not recommended, compared to other candidate assays, that there are other candidate assays that are passing the Target Product Profile (TPP). Sedia does not have access to all the assays evaluated but it does not believe there are currently other assays that meet the TPP. It acknowledges that there may be other assays that estimate incidence better than the BED EIA, which is now over 10 years old. Sedia believes that in all of these evaluations, the assessment on whether an assay should be used should be a more pragmatic one of determining what assay is best to use for any of various populations, situations and purposes, instead of making an absolute recommendation against all use of assays when there is no assay that passes the TPP. The Sedia™ HIV-1 BED Incidence EIA has been found suitable by researchers, particularly where other assays were not available in the past, where all of the recommended problem specimens were excluded from incidence estimation, where specific subtype populations are evaluated or where ongoing trending of data is being collected to compare to historical data previously collected using the BED EIA.

- 3) The high FRR in this study may be influenced by multiple factors already cited, including the longer MDRI calculated in this study, the possible non-exclusion of certain individuals likely to provide false recent results, and possible distribution of unverified subtypes in this study.
- 4) The authors state that they do not believe varying of thresholds or use of currently described RITA algorithms will improve the performance of the assay. However, no data has been presented to this effect. At the same time, other researchers have reported algorithms incorporating the BED EIA which gave improved false positive rates.
- 5) All BED EIA's to date have been manufactured using a single lot of antigen. Sedia has recently had a new lot manufactured, which has the same sequence as the original lot, and is currently qualifying it, much as any other assay manufacturer qualifies subsequent lots of antigen for their assays. Data collected thus far support good comparability between lots. This does not represent a change in antigen, but rather a new lot of antigen. In any event, the product release criteria of both Sedia and CDC (which will continue to test and release BED EIA kits) will not change as a result of a raw material lot change. It's unclear whether CEPHIA expects to limit their conclusions on all incidence assays to changes in antigen lots or other key raw materials which can potentially have an effect on product performance if not qualified by accepted industry methods.

Technical Appraisal

Assay Kits and Reagents

Sedia disputes the characterization that the feature of removable strips and individual wells “may cause problems if the plate washer in use cannot be programmed on an individual well/strip basis.” This is not a problem given the simple solution offered in the insert to use blank wells or strips in unused portions of the plates, an approach that both other customers and Sedia scientists have successfully used. Obviously there are many procedures in any assay that are problems if there are no solutions or directions on how to address them. Sedia feels this feature of the assay is a significant benefit to users in saving cost and reducing waste, not a problem that needs to be resolved.

25°C Incubator

The report has stated that some laboratories may find the requirement for this incubator an issue. Certainly if a laboratory doesn't have any of the required equipment, this is likely to be an issue. Sedia believes it is not unreasonable to expect labs equipped with all the other remaining equipment required to run any EIA (a plate washer, plate reader, 37°C incubator, a water system, and calibrated pipettes, etc) to also have a 25°C incubator. Furthermore, it should be noted that the “Acceptable Performance” criteria in the TPP includes incubation up to 25°C, so even by the expectation established by the Working Group that established the TPP, use of an incubator at this temperature should not be unrealistic.

Associated documentation

2. BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA Data Management Worksheet

The report firstly states that the Sedia™ BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA “is intended to be used with a customized spreadsheet which is used to validate the run and calculates ODN values”. This is incorrectly worded suggesting that the user is required to use the spreadsheet, which is not the case. The BED EIA is not intended to be used with the spreadsheet, but may be used with it. It is not required. The spreadsheet however, is intended to be used with the BED EIA, if a user so wishes. Considerable discussion is presented regarding changes needed and made to the BED HIV-1 Incidence EIA Data Management Worksheet over 2 years ago. These issues should no longer apply to current users (who the report acknowledges were notified of the changes) or new users, who would access the Worksheet on Sedia’s website. Sedia provided the Worksheet originally developed by the CDC for download by customers, but did not have access to the Worksheet content which was locked. As noted in the report, CEPHIA advised Sedia of errors it had identified. Sedia verified the errors and reported these to the CDC, which implemented corrections and provided Sedia with corrected Worksheets. At that time Sedia gained access to the Worksheet coding and could do its own internal software validation. Once this was completed, the software was uploaded onto the Sedia website and customers were notified of the updated Worksheet. Sedia appreciates CEPHIA’s notification of the Worksheet issues and currently has the means to evaluate reported errors, correct and validate them in a more timely manner. There have been no reports of errors since these corrections were implemented in February 2013. The report also references only one of two spreadsheets available on the website (i.e. LN-6083 for Excel 2007 and later). A version for Excel versions prior to 2007 (LN-6082) is and has been available on the website since the corrections were implemented.

CEPHIA has recommended a comprehensive method of informing users of changes. Sedia’s policy is to notify all customers of major substantive changes to the Worksheets or to the Product Inserts, and has done so to date. Major substantive changes are those likely to impact results or interpretation of data due to changes in procedures, calculations, validity ranges, cutoffs, MDRI, assay design or critical interpretations. Minor changes are typically those to update background scientific literature, provide clarification of wording, update company related information (new products, website links, etc) and notification is not routinely provided to customers for these. Users should note that Sedia Customer Service will notify the purchaser of the product of such changes, however the purchaser may not be the actual user. Users should ensure that the purchaser passes on any communications about the assay to them. Additionally, Sedia has a Facebook page and Twitter account which are intended to be used for such notifications as well. Users may link to those media (located on the top right corner of the Sedia website) to keep up to date on major changes in technical literature.

Target Product Profile

There are several issues with the Target Product Profile in terms of the Sedia™ HIV-1 BED Incidence EIA’s fit. Sedia recommends CEPHIA use a consistent format for how this column is reported. For example, the Sedia™ HIV-1 LAg-Avidity EIA TPP table simply enters “Acceptable” for those items that comply rather than the actual value or result as is done with the BED EIA TPP.

- Intended Use False Recency Rate (FRR) is dependent on population tested and study design. CEPHIA has determined the

assay is not appropriate for solo use in incidence calculations, but the FRR has been reported to be low in some populations. Sedia believes that in such situations the use of the BED EIA may still be of utility, particularly where long term trending analysis is taking place and changing to another assay may produce an artificial jump or decline in incidence due to limitations of, or performance differences of the replacement assay

- Target Population Sedia disagrees with the blanket statement that the assay is not appropriate for international population based incidence surveillance. It may be less preferable than other newer assays, but some applications (e.g. primarily Subtype B populations in various countries, populations with appropriate subject exclusions are tested, populations that have historically been tested with BED EIA and for which the researchers are looking to monitor trends or changes in incidence rates, as opposed to absolute rates) may be suitable for this assay, assuming CDC guidelines for use of the assay are followed. In fact, several customers aware of the BED EIA limitations raised by CEPHIA continue to purchase the assay for such purposes.
- False Recent Rate (FRR) The calculated FRR appears to be based on a general population excluding treated subjects and elite controllers, but not individuals with AIDS or elevated CD4+ T cell counts, as directed by the product insert and CDC guidelines. The FRR can be lower in some populations particularly where appropriate exclusions are applied, as have been published in the literature.
- Mean Duration Within the acceptable range but significantly different than CDC calculated MDRI. Sedia is unable to ascertain the basis of the difference from the data provided.
- Algorithm CEPHIA finds no value for the use of this assay in an algorithm, yet the assay was only evaluated in the report as a solo test, not in any algorithm
- Analyte Incorrectly stated as gp41. Assay analyte is anti-HIV-1 (gp41) antibodies
- Sample Type Does not state that assay also can test fresh serum or plasma
- Sample Volume Incorrectly listed as 40 µL. Minimum is 5 µL, maximum (with retest in triplicate) is 20 µL
- Storage/Shipping Conditions Storage Conditions should be -25 to -10°C and 2-8°C; Shipping conditions are cold (nominally 2-15°C) with ice packets.
- Incubation Temperature Incorrectly lists -25°C as an incubation temperature. This was probably intended to be +25°C, which is the incubation temperature for the substrate.
- Shelf Life Actual shelf life not stated. Shelf life is currently 24 months from date of manufacture.

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The Conclusions and recommendations are of the authors and do not constitute an endorsement of any of the products by their employing organisations.